

Center-of-Mass, Schrodinger Bound State and Hydrodynamics

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There have been various derivations of the Schrodinger equation in the literature (e.g. (1)) based on hydrodynamics (continuity and conservation of momentum equations) with the added assumption that a velocity field $u(x,t) = d/dx S(x,t)$ where $S(x,t)$ is a new field. Furthermore a mathematical transformation $Wv = \sqrt{d(x,t)} \exp(i S(x,t))$ is used leading to the new function $Wv(x)$.

In (2) we compared the bound state Schrodinger scenario to the hydrodynamic equations in (1). In (1) $d u(x,t)/dt = -dV/dx -dW/dx$ ((1)). $V(x)$ is the usual potential and $W(x)$ is described as a fluid stress potential. We also compared (1) to a free quantum particle and found that $S(x,t)$ must contain a $-Et$ piece if the hydrodynamical approach is to match quantum mechanics. In (1), ((1)) is shown to be equivalent to: $d/dt \text{partial } S + \frac{1}{2} u(x,t)u(x,t) + W(x) + V(x) = 0$ ((2)) with W being expressed in terms of spatial derivatives of density. $d/dt \text{partial } S$ yields $-E$ and $u(x,t)=0$ for a bound state so ((2)) is of the form of a conservation of energy equation. If a free quantum particle is described spatially by $\exp(ipx)$ then one may create a distribution $\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and calculate average kinetic energy $[-1/2m \text{Sum over } p a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)] / [\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)]$ and set it equal to $W(x)$ as done in (2).

In this note, we wish to examine the idea of a free particle conditional probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and compare it to the Schrodinger bound state which itself may be considered a localized solution if one ignores the internal wavefunction and considers only the center of mass features $\exp(-i(\text{masses} + En) t + ip\text{overall } x)$ where $p(\text{overall}) = 0$. We argue that center of mass features are contained in the Schrodinger bound state solution if one integrates over x relative to cm , the x variable in the Schrodinger equation. The idea of time t only applies to the cm , there is no time in $\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Furthermore $p(\text{overall}) = 0$ only if one integrates $W(x)$ ($-i/dx W$) over all x (relative to cm). Also the form $-i d/dx \text{Wavefunction}(\text{free particle } p) = p \text{Wavefunction}(\text{free particle})$ where $\text{Conditional Prob} = \exp(-iEt+ipx)$ carries over to the bound state with: $-i d/dx \exp(\ln(Wv)) = \{-i d/dx \ln(Wv)\} \exp(\ln(Wv))$ where $Wv = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. In other words there is an imaginary momentum $-i/dx \ln(Wv(x))$ at each x in the bound solution so $u(x,t)=0$ holds for the real part. As a result, the hydrodynamical approach to quantum mechanics is not as straightforward as it may appear on the surface.

We try to investigate a number of ideas related to the treatment of quantum bound states using hydrodynamics.

Schrodinger Equation and Special Relativity

The Schrodinger equation is nonrelativistic, nevertheless the conditional probability (wavefunction) for a free particle $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is written in a relativistic form i.e. $-Et+px$ is a Lorentzinvariant if the relativistic E and p are used. For the Schrodinger equation, the nonrelativistic values of E and p are used i.e. $E=pp/2m_0$ and $p=mv$.

In previous notes (3) we have argued that special relativity, classical waves (sound, light) and quantum free particles are associated with two flow/flux equations:

$\frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } A(x,t) = p$ ((3a)) and $\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } A(x,t) = -E$ ((3b)) with $A(x,t) = -Et + px$

For the quantum free particle these are associated with an eigenvalue equation i.e. linked to conditional probability:

$-i \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } \exp(iA) = p \exp(iA)$ ((4a)) and $i \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } \exp(iA) = E \exp(iA)$ ((4b))

In other words instead of obtaining p and $-E$ on the RHS one obtains these values multiplied by their free particle conditional probability. One has a steady state probability picture with E and p nevertheless.

Bound State Quantum Solution

Given that a free particle is represented by a conditional probability of $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ one must consider how to describe a bound particle under the influence of a potential. This leads to a number of issues:

1. Even though one has a bound particle which ranges in x from $-\infty$ to ∞ in the time-independent Schrodinger equation, a bound object is considered to be localized and one may replace the entire system with a free particle with an adjusted mass. In other words, one may take Energy overall = $-E_n + \text{masses}$ ($c=1$) where E_n is the energy value from the time independent Schrodinger equation. This center of mass solution should have the free particle conditional probability of $\exp(-\text{Energy overall} * t + i p(\text{overall}) x)$ where $p(\text{overall})=0$.
2. From the Schrodinger equation (time-independent) one obtains a specific E_n , but there is a $KE(x)$ as well as a $pave(x)$ i.e. $[-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} Wv] / Wv$ and $-i \frac{dWv}{dx} / Wv$ respectively. To find the overall momentum describing the cm motion, one must integrate over all x . This leads to $p(\text{overall}) = 0$. (A special average is needed namely one weighted by density $WvWv$.)
In the hydrodynamical approach $u(x,t)$ is real so for a bound state $u(x,t)=0$, but this is not the full picture it seems.
3. The center of mass may be characterized by x_{cm} and t . There exists x (relative to cm), but time is represented by one clock (in the nonrelativistic case) and that should be the cm one which governs time resolution of the overall system i.e. $1/E_n$. As a result, $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ where $E = p^2/2m$ which applies to a free particle should be replaced with $\exp(ipx)$ which is no longer a Lorentz invariant. One may show that each p for a free particle within a bound state is actually linked to E_n the overall energy. To do so write $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$ and $Wv = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ in the time-independent Schrodinger equation and collect factors of $\exp(ipx)$:

$$.5 a(p_1) p_1 p_1/2m + \text{Sum over } k V_k a(p_1-k) = E_n a(p_1)$$

Thus any p_1 is associated with the same E_n .

Even though (x,t) is of the form a 4-vector, using averages shows that x and t are not on the same footing.

4. The form $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ maintains a similar form in the average case with $\exp(ipx)$ being replaced by $Wv(x)$ and p by $-i\hbar Wv/dx / Wv$, the average momentum i.e.

$$-i\hbar/dx \exp(\ln Wv) = (-d\ln Wv/dx) \exp(\ln Wv) \quad ((5))$$

$\ln(Wv)$ appears to be more of an “information” type of term than the portion of a Lorentz invariant i.e. px . To find the overall p corresponding to the cm free particle one needs to integrate overall x (which is really x relative to cm, but runs from -infinite to infinite).

$B = \int dx Wv Wv (-i\hbar Wv/dx) / Wv = \int dx -i\hbar Wv Wv/dx = 0$ because $Wv Wv$ is 0 at its endpoints. One may note that average performed is a special one, namely $\text{density} = Wv Wv$ (Wv real for a bound state) multiplied by the value: $-i\hbar d/dx \ln(Wv)$. Similarly, to find out the number of particles one uses: $\int dx Wv Wv = 1$.

Averaging related to values describing the center of mass object includes the $\text{density} = Wv Wv$ weight. This is reminiscent of hydrodynamics in which one sees quantities such as $\text{density}(x,t) u(x,t)$. In other words this type of averaging seems to bring in the “macroscopic” fluid dynamical picture into quantum mechanics, while underneath there is the periodicity/interference behaviour of the free quantum particle conditional probabilities $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This free quantum behaviour, however, has implications for the macroscopic results such as density and helps to explain why hydrodynamical approaches use the mathematical transformation $Wv = \sqrt{\text{density}} \exp(i S(x,t))$.

We argue that this helps to explain the quantum statistical average which must be performed over all space:

$$\int dx Wv^*(x) [\text{Operator or } f(x)] Wv(x) \quad ((6))$$

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ on the other hand has: $\exp(iEt-ipx)\exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1$ at each x and so is local, not global like the bound state. The bound state is not localized at a point, but is “localized” in the region from -infinite to infinite with most of the density usually being in a somewhat small region (e.g. for the quantum oscillator most of the density is within the classical turning points).

Hydrodynamical Approach

The hydrodynamical approach uses the continuity equation and a transport -conservation of momentum equation together with the assumption: $u(x,t) = \text{velocity field} = 1/m d/dx S(x,t)$. For a free particle $S(x,t) = -Et+px$. Thus, $u(x,t) = p$. We argue that it is interesting to consider p as a velocity field because in the probabilistic approach the probability to be at any x is $P(x) = \exp(iEt-ipx) \exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1$. Thus the probabilistic

approach does describe a kind of flow which maintains constant $P(x)$, but nevertheless contains E and p . This leads to a periodic object $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ associated with probability and a frequency proportional to $1/E$ and a wavelength to $1/p$.

Secondly the hydrodynamical approach defines a function $Wv(x)$ such that:

$$Wv = \sqrt{\text{density}(x,t)} \exp(i S(x,t)) \quad \hbar=1 \quad ((7))$$

Given that Wv ultimately is the wavefunction, ((7)) shows that for a bound state $S(x,t) = -Et$. In the hydrodynamical approach, ((7)) is introduced as a math transformation, but we argue it is based on the physics of a quantum free particle and its extension to a momentum distribution. We argue that it is too drastic to simply introduce ((7)) as a math transformation without examining its implications i.e. for a free particle it is equivalent to:

$$-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \exp(-iEt+ipx) = p \exp(-iEt+ipx) \text{ which leads to a probabilistic view.}$$

Given this view one may formulate the Schrodinger equation using average kinetic energy i.e.:

$$[-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dWv}{dx}] / Wv + V(x) = E_n \text{ with } Wv = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

The hydrodynamic approach instead uses:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{full } u(x,t) = -\frac{dV}{dx} - \frac{dW}{dx} \quad ((9))$$

where $W(x)$ is a fluid stress potential linked to $\langle (v_i - u_i)(v_j - u_j) \rangle$ written in terms of derivatives of density (as an assumption). In (1) an equation equivalent to ((9)) is given as:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } S + \frac{1}{2} u(x,t)u(x,t) + W(x) + V(x) = 0 \quad ((2)) \quad ((10))$$

For a bound state, $u(x,t)=0$ which is equivalent to working in the center of mass frame we argue. $S=-Et$ so the first term on the LHS of ((10)) gives energy. In ((7)) energy calculated in the center of mass frame becomes part of the description of the center of mass itself i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$. ((10)) leads to the conservation equation:

$$W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((11))$$

Thus $W(x)$ should be average kinetic energy. Given that the hydrodynamical equation is consistent with a free quantum particle $d(x,t)=1$ and $S(x,t) = -Et+px$ it seems one may construct $W(x)$ using:

$$W(x) = [-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dWv}{dx}] / Wv \text{ where } Wv = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx)$$

as argued in (3).

One may note how $W(x)$ differs from classical statistical mechanics with the ideal gas law. In such a case there is also a force/pressure balance (i.e. take d/dx of ((11))), but pressure is proportional to density because average kinetic energy at each x is proportional to T . For the quantum case $KE(x)$ and one does not use $WvWv$ $(-1/2m d/dx dWv/dx)/Wv$ for $KE(x)$, but rather:

$$KE(x) = -1/2m d/dx dWv/dx / Wv \quad ((12))$$

It is the derivative of ((12)) which balances $-dV/dx$. This is a local quantity. It is not an average of a quantity using the weight $Wv(x)Wv(x)$ because one does not integrate over all x .

Force versus Potential

Classical mechanics seems to focus on force as the cause of acceleration. The potential $V(x)$ appears to be a mathematical construct which is useful in a conservation equation. For example, a hydrodynamics fluid equation (based on conservation of momentum) (1):

$$d/dt \text{ partial } \{m d(x,t) u_i(x,t)\} + d/dx_j \{s_{ij} d(x,t)\} + d(x,t) dV/dx_i = 0 \quad ((13))$$

uses force i.e. $-dV/dx$.

As a result, it is interesting that the hydrodynamical approach (which is classical in nature) seeks to remove d/dx derivatives from dW/dx and dV/dx in ((9)) to obtain a conservation type of equation ((10)), ((11)). The time-independent Schrodinger equation is of the form of a local conservation of energy equation - there is no acceleration (except for $v_{rms}(x)$), but we argue that $V(x)$ delivers momentum impulses, a role played by force in classical mechanics. For example:

$$[-1/2m d/dx dWv/dx]/Wv + V(x) = E_n \rightarrow -1/2m d/dx dWv/dx + VWv = E_n Wv \quad ((14))$$

If one writes $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ and $Wv = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ then:

$$V_k \exp(ikx) a(p) \exp(ipx) = V_k a(p) \exp(i(k+p)x) \quad ((15))$$

In other words the potential which has units of energy has delivered a momentum impulse of k . Furthermore it is $\exp(ipx)$ related to the free particle probability which also has a form capable of delivering an impulse of p . One may write an expression for quantum bound force i.e.

$$-dV/dx = d/dx \{ [-1/2m d/dx dWv/dx]/Wv \} \quad ((16))$$

,but impulse delivery is already contained in $V(x)Wv(x)$. Thus in quantum mechanics the potential is not simply a mathematical construct as the Bohm-Aharonov experiment shows.

Conclusion

In conclusion we investigate the classical hydrodynamical approach to obtaining the Schrodinger equation (1) which assumes: $u(x,t)=\text{velocity field} = d/dx \text{ partial } S(x,t)$. We have already argued in (2) that for a free particle this is equivalent to two flow/flux equations: $d/dx \text{ partial } A = p$ and $d/dt \text{ partial } = -E$ with $A=-Et+px$. These may be written as eigenvalue equations to bring in a probabilistic picture. In this note we investigate the relationship between the hydrodynamical approach and the flow/flux equations for a bound quantum state and argue that in such a state a free particle state representing the entire bound system seen as a new entity should emerge. We also investigate some ideas which seem to be present such as the need to calculate density weighted averages of the bound state to find information about the new entity.

References

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